

CACAO: A Research Software Platform for the Cloud

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Abstract—This paper introduces CACAO, a research software platform that strives to simplify the use of cloud computing for research and education. CACAO’s cloud automation and continuous analysis features make it easy to deploy scientific workflows or educational environments in the cloud using templates. The platform has been expanding its support for different cloud service providers and improving scalability, making it more widely applicable for a variety of projects. This paper provides an overview of CACAO’s key features and its use cases.

Index Terms—cloud computing, cloud automation, continuous analysis, cloud orchestration, scientific research, cyberinfrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of cloud computing has brought significant changes in the research computing landscape, allowing researchers to conduct data analysis with an unprecedented level of compute and storage capabilities. However, performing research computing in the cloud differs greatly from traditional environments that use high performance computing (HPC) clusters or local workstations [1] [2], introducing operational challenges. The complexity of cloud services and cost containment is still a barrier for some users. Researchers and educators require tooling that simplify the deployment of software for research and teaching purposes in the cloud.

CACAO (Cloud Automation & Continuous Analysis Orchestration) is a platform for researchers and educators that enables multi-cloud orchestration. It aims to simplify the usage of cloud computing by providing a streamlined web interface, flexibility, and collaboration. By utilizing CACAO, researchers can effortlessly deploy research workflows to various cloud services. Educators can leverage CACAO to create cloud resources for hundreds of students [3]. Moreover, research software engineers can build new research platforms on top of CACAO that can operate on multiple clouds without vendor lock-in.

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II. DESIGN

CACAO consists of event-driven microservices built on top of Kubernetes [4] as shown in Fig. 1. CACAO uses a microservice design, where each microservice is responsible for implementing specific tasks such as cloud resource orchestration, data management, user management, and accounting. The deployment, discovery, scaling, and monitoring of these microservices are managed by Kubernetes, providing the resiliency and scalability to the system.

Fig. 1. CACAO system design. CACAO consists of several Kubernetes-based microservices represented as blue boxes. It is capable of coordinating various cloud resources to deploy user-requested research applications or services using templates. Green boxes represent external components of CACAO, and black arrow lines represent control flows. It offers both web and command-line interfaces for users and administrators.

CACAO integrates with domain specific languages (DSLs) [5] or infrastructure-as-code (IaC) [6] *templates* that enable researchers and software engineers to easily deploy cloud resources or software stacks. The templates are stored in git repositories, which makes them available for collaboration and version control. By utilizing known templates languages, rather than developing yet another proprietary cloud-native language for CACAO, researchers will have more resources to learn template development, create more sustainable templates using established DSLs, and make their research workflows and system configurations more accessible for their community, facilitating collaborative research and enhancing reproducibility.

III. USE CASE

CACAO can be utilized for a wide range of projects and outcomes. This section highlights several use cases from

ongoing, funded projects that utilize CACAO. It is worth noting that each use case is not mutually exclusive, meaning that a project can utilize CACAO for training, Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), Software-as-a-Service (SaaS), and sustainability platform simultaneously.

A. As a development platform

Developers can create software development environments quickly using templates in CACAO. The cloud resources created using templates can include a complex cluster configuration or a range of tools for software development. For instance, developers can create a Kubernetes software development environment that requires multi-node K3s [7] installation and various development tools – including Go [8] compiler, Docker [9], Skaffold [10], and Visual Studio Code [11]. CACAO enables a rapid deployment process for setting up new environments for testing new features or dependency versions, leading to faster development cycles. The research software engineering team developing CACAO uses the platform internally in this way.

B. As a best practices platform

As software systems become increasingly complex, with multiple dependencies and intricate configurations, software installation can often be challenging and may not always go as planned. For instance, some software systems may require specific dependency versions to ensure stability or optimal performance, making it difficult for novice users to follow the installation process correctly. Security is another challenge for users who are not knowledgeable about networking best practices or systems hardening. CACAO addresses these challenges by allowing template authors to incorporate best practices for the software they maintain and share these configurations with their community.

C. As an education and training platform

Educators can utilize CACAO to easily configure experimental environments for classes or workshops. With CACAO's templates, educators can quickly create custom environments tailored to the needs of their students, without the need for extensive technical expertise. In 2022, CACAO was utilized in six public workshops with nearly 200 students across three countries [12] [13] [14] [15] [16] [17]. These workshops taught topics ranging from earth science, bioinformatics, and machine learning using Tensorflow [18]. Instructors in these workshops relied on CACAO to provision Kubernetes clusters with a large number of nodes using Zero to Jupyterhub [19] and standard virtual machine instances, some of which were using GPUs.

D. As a software-as-a-service platform

Researchers can launch on-demand research workflows. Diffusion Approximation for Demographic Inference (DADI) [20] is a workflow that infer models of demographic history and distributions of fitness effects from population genomics data using machine learning. The Open Forest Observatory (OFO) [21] project provides data analysis workflows and

software for monitoring forest health using aerial images. CACAO deploys and manages workflows and software in the AWS and Jetstream2 [22] and software on behalf of the researchers, making research process more efficient.

E. As an infrastructure-as-a-service platform

CACAO can be used as an infrastructure for research projects. BisQue (Bio-Image Semantic Query User Environment) [23] is a research platform that enables researchers to manage and analyze image data in a diverse range of research domains, including biology, environmental science, and geology. HydroGEN [24] is a platform for hydrologic scenario generation using machine learning to facilitate research on national water resources in the United States. With the assistance of CACAO, these projects can operate on diverse cloud platforms, such as on-premise Kubernetes cluster, AWS, and JetStream2, irrespective of their technical differences. Future integration includes adding the ability to scale the infrastructure up and down depending on the workload for the flexibility and cost-efficiency.

F. As a sustainability platform

Although CACAO cannot address every aspect of research software sustainability [25] [26], it enhances the process of deploying software in the cloud, thereby increasing accessibility to the software. Once a template is created by research software engineers, researchers who are users of the template can consistently deploy the software seamlessly, allowing a community to test, validate, and benchmark the research software without having to follow technical instructions on installing and configuring software manually. Additionally, CACAO allows developers to semantically match templates to the appropriate cloud and cloud resources, reducing the confusion that may arise when a user may not be as familiar with the variety of cloud options. Ultimately, CACAO is designed to be extensible by providing a path to integrate future frameworks and clouds, offering research software engineers an option to extend their software sustainability over time.

IV. CONCLUSION

CACAO is a cloud platform that aims to simplify the use of cloud computing in scientific research and education. With ongoing efforts from the development team to enhance its capabilities, such as expanding support for various cloud providers, improving recoverability, and better cost budgeting, CACAO has the potential to become a widely-used platform in scientific research and education and help empower the research software engineering community in using the cloud. Current requirements for the platform have been largely acquired through collaborations in the life sciences, earth sciences, and space sciences, and further research into multi-cloud approaches in other domains is needed. CACAO is currently available on Jetstream2 with an ACCESS account at <https://cacao.jetstream-cloud.org>. CACAO's primary code repository can be found at <https://gitlab.com/cyverse/CACAO>.

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